

STUDIES ON THE ENGLISH MODAL AUXILIARIES

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Annotation: There are purely modal verbs, their equivalents and multifunctional verbs in the role of modal verbs. The article deals with the stylistic and lexicographic analysis of modal verbs in English, their use, analysis.

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At present, the meaning and the role of modal verbs in English can be observed in the formal-structural approach. Thus, English modal verbs is a group of verbs that express the attitude towards an action, but not the action itself. In other words, modal verbs help the speaker to show that he considers a certain action possible or impossible, necessary or unnecessary, etc. The following verbs have all of the above properties, and can be classed as the principal modal verbs of English. **The English Modal verbs** are a subset of the English auxiliary verbs used mostly to express modality (properties such as possibility, obligation, etc.). They can be distinguished from other verbs by their defectiveness (they do not have participle or infinitive forms) and by their neutralization (that they do not take the ending *-(e)s* in the third-person singular).

The Principal English Modal verbs are *can, could, may, might, shall, should, will, would, and must*. Certain other verbs are sometimes, but not always, classed as modals; these include *ought, had better, and (in certain uses) dare and need*. Verbs which share only some of the characteristics of the principal modals are sometimes called "quasi-modals", "semi-modals", or "pseudo-modals".

The verbs customarily classed as modals in English have the following properties:

They do not inflect (in the modern language) except insofar as some of them come in present–past (present–preterite) pairs. They do not add the ending *-(e)s* in the third-person singular (the present-tense modals therefore follow the preterite-present paradigm).

They are defective: they are not used as infinitives or participles (except occasionally in non-standard English; see below), nor as imperatives, nor (in the standard way) as subjunctives. They function as auxiliary verbs : they modify the modality of another verb, which they govern. This verb generally appears as a bare infinitive, although in some definitions, a modal verb can also govern the *to*-infinitive (as in the case of *ought*). They have the syntactic properties associated with auxiliary verbs in English, principally that they can undergo subject-auxiliary inversion (in questions, for example) and can be negated by the appending of *not* after the verb.

The following verbs have all of the above properties, and can be classed as the principal modal verbs of English. They are listed here in present–preterite pairs where applicable:

- *can* and *could*
- *may* and *might*
- *shall* and *should*
- *will* and *would*
- *must*

Note that the preterite forms are not necessarily used to refer to past time, and in some cases, they are near-synonyms to the present forms. Note that most of these so-called preterite forms are most often used in the subjunctive mood in the present tense.

The auxiliary verbs *may* and *let* are also used often in the subjunctive mood. Famous examples of these are "May The Force be with you." and "Let God bless you with good." These are both sentences that express some uncertainty; hence they are subjunctive sentences.

The verbs listed below mostly share the above features but with certain differences. They are sometimes, but not always, categorized as modal verbs. They may also be called "semi-modals".

The verb *ought* differs from the principal modals only in that it governs a *to*-infinitive rather than a bare infinitive (compare *he should go* with *he ought to go*).

The verbs *dare* and *need* can be used as modals, often in the negative (*Dare he fight?*; *You dare not do that.*; *You need not go.*), although they are more commonly found in constructions where they appear as ordinary inflected verbs (*He dares to fight*; *You don't need to go*). The verb *had* in the expression *had better* behaves like a modal verb, hence *had better* (considered as a compound verb) is sometimes classed as a modal or semi-modal.

Other English auxiliaries appear in a variety of different forms and are not regarded as modal verbs.

Etymology

The modals *can* and *could* are from Old English *can(n)* and *cub*, which were respectively present and preterite forms of the verb *cunnan* ("to be able"). The silent *l* in the spelling of *could* results from analogy with *would* and *should*.

Similarly, *may* and *might* are from Old English *mæg* and *meahte*, respectively present and preterite forms of *magan* ("may, to be able"); *shall* and *should* are from *sceal* and *sceolde*, respectively present and preterite forms of *sculan* ("to owe, be obliged");

The aforementioned Old English verbs *cunnan*, *magan*, *sculan*, and *willan* followed the preterite-present paradigm (or, in the case of *willan*, a similar but irregular paradigm), which explains the absence of the ending *-s* in the third person on the present forms *can*, *may*, *shall*, and *will*. (The original Old English forms given above were first and third person singular forms; their descendant forms became generalized to all persons and numbers.)

The verb *must* comes from Old English *moste*, part of the verb *motan* ("to be able to, be obliged to"). This was another preterite-present verb, of which *moste* was in fact the preterite (the present form *mot* gave rise to *mote*, which was used as a modal verb in Early Modern English; but *must* has now lost its past connotations and has replaced *mote*). Similarly, *ought* was originally a past form—it derives from *ahte*, preterite of *agan* ("to own"), another Old English preterite-present verb, whose present tense form *ah* has also given the modern (regular) verb *owe* (and *ought* was formerly used as a past tense of *owe*).

The verb *dare* also originates from a preterite-present verb, *durran* ("to dare"), specifically its present tense *dear(r)*, although in its non-modal uses in Modern English it is conjugated regularly. However, *need* comes from the regular Old English verb *neodian* (meaning "to be necessary")—the alternative third person form *need* (in place of *needs*), which has become the norm in modal uses, became common in the 16th century.

Syntax

A modal verb serves as an auxiliary to another verb, which appears in the infinitive form (the bare infinitive, or the *to*-infinitive in the cases of *ought* and *used as* discussed above). Examples: *You must escape*; *This may be difficult*.

The verb governed by the modal may be another auxiliary (necessarily one that can appear in infinitive form—this includes *be* and *have*, but not another modal). Hence a modal may introduce a chain of verb forms, in which the other auxiliaries express properties such as aspect and voice, as in *He must have been given a new job*.

Modals can appear in tag questions and other elliptical sentences without the governed verb being expressed: *...can he?*; *I mustn't.*; *Would they?*

Like other auxiliaries, modal verbs are negated by the addition of the word *not* after them. (The modification of meaning may not always correspond to simple negation, as in the case of *must not*.) The modal word *can* combine with *not* forms the single word *cannot*. Most of the modals have contracted negated forms in *n't* which are commonly used in informal English: *can't*, *mustn't*, *won't* (from *will*), etc.

Again like other auxiliaries, modal verbs undergo inversion with their subject, in forming questions and in the other cases described in the article on subject-auxiliary inversion: *Could you do this?*; *On no account may you enter*. When there is negation, the contraction with *n't* may undergo inversion as an auxiliary in its own right: *Why can't I come in?* (or: *Why can I not come in?*).

More information on these topics can be found at English clause syntax.

Past forms

The preterite (past) forms given above (*could*, *might*, *should*, and *would*, corresponding to *can*, *may*, *shall*, and *will*, respectively) do not always simply modify the meaning of the modal to give it past time reference. The only one regularly used as an ordinary past tense is *could*, when referring to ability: *I could swim* may serve as a past form of *I can swim*.

All the preterites are used as past equivalents for the corresponding present modals in indirect speech and similar clauses requiring the rules of sequence of tenses to be applied. For example, in 1960, it might have been said that *People **think** that we **will** all be driving hover cars by the year 2000*, whereas at a later date it might be reported that *In 1960, people **thought** we **would** all be driving hover cars by the year 2000*.

This "future-in-the-past" (also known as the past prospective, see: prospective) usage of *would* can also occur in independent sentences: *I moved to Green Gables in 1930; I would live there for the next ten years*.

In many cases, in order to give modals past reference, they are used together with a "perfect infinitive", namely the auxiliary *have* and a past participle, as in *I should have asked her*; *You may have seen me*. Sometimes these expressions are limited in meaning; for example, *must have* can refer only to certainty, whereas past obligation is expressed by an alternative phrase such as *had to*;

Replacements for defective forms

As noted above, English modal verbs are defective in that they do not have infinitive, participle, imperative, or (standard) subjunctive forms, and, in some cases, past forms. However in many cases there exist equivalent expressions that carry the same meaning as the modal, and can be used to supply the missing forms. In particular:

The modals *can* and *could*, in their meanings expressing ability, can be replaced by *am/is/are able to* and *was/were able to*. Additional forms can thus be supplied: the infinitive (*to*) *be able to*, the subjunctive and (rarely) imperative *be able to*, and the participles *being able to* and *been able to*.

The modals *may* and *might*, in their meanings expressing permission, can be replaced by *am/is/are allowed to* and *was/were allowed to*. The modal *must* in most meanings can be replaced by *have/has to*. This supplies the past and past participle form *had to*, and other forms (*to*) *have to*, *having to*. *Will* can be replaced by *am/is/are going to*. This can supply the past and other forms: *was/were going to*, (*to*) *be going to*, *being/been going to*. The modals *should* and *ought to* might be replaced by *am/is/are supposed to*, thus supplying the forms *was/were supposed to*, (*to*) *be supposed to*, *being/been supposed to*.

Contractions and reduced pronunciation

As already mentioned, most of the modals in combination with *not* form commonly used contractions: *can't*, *won't*, etc. Some of the modals also have contracted forms themselves:

The verb *will* is often contracted to *'ll*; the same contraction may also represent *shall*.

The verb *would* (or *should*, when used as a first-person equivalent of *would*) is often contracted to *'d*.

The *had* of *had better* is also often contracted to *'d*. (The same contraction is also used for other cases of *had* as an auxiliary.)

Certain of the modals generally have a weak pronunciation when they are not stressed or otherwise prominent; for example, *can* is usually pronounced /kən/. The same applies to certain words following modals, particularly auxiliary *have*: a combination like *should have* is normally reduced to /ʃʊd(h)əv/ or just /ʃʊdə/ "shoul'da". Also *ought to* can become /ɔ:tə/ "oughta".

Usage of specific verbs

Can and could

The modal verb *can* expresses possibility in a dynamic, deontic, epistemic sense, that is, in terms of innate ability, permissibility, or possible circumstance. For example:

I can speak English means "I am able to speak English" or "I know how to speak English."

You can smoke here means "you may (are permitted to) smoke here" (in formal English *may* or *might* is sometimes considered more correct than *can* or *could* in these senses).

The preterite form *could* is used as the past tense or conditional form of *can* in the above meanings. It is also used to express possible circumstance: *We could be in trouble here*. It is preferable to use *could*, *may* or *might* rather than *can* when expressing possible circumstance in a particular situation (as opposed to the general case, as in the "rivalry" example above, where *can* or *may* is used).

Both *can* and *could* can be used to make requests: *Can/could you pass me the cheese?* means "Please pass me the cheese" (where *could* indicates greater politeness). The use of *could* with the perfect infinitive expresses past ability or possibility, either in some counterfactual circumstance (*I could have told him if I had seen him*), or in some real circumstance where the act in question was not in fact realized: *I could have told him yesterday* (but in fact I didn't). The use of *can* with the perfect infinitive, *can have...*, is a rarer alternative to *may have...* (for the negative see below).

The negation of *can* is the single word *cannot*, only occasionally written separately as *cannot*. Though *cannot* is preferred (as *cannot* is potentially ambiguous), its irregularity (all other uncontracted verbal negations use at least two words) sometimes causes those unfamiliar with the nuances of English spelling to use the separated form.

The negative forms reverse the meaning of the modal (to express inability, impermissibility or impossibility). This differs from the case with *may* or *might* used to express possibility: *it can't be true* has a different meaning than *it may not be true*. Thus *can't* (or *cannot*) is often used to express disbelief in the possibility of something, as *must* expresses belief in the certainty of something. When the circumstance in question refers to the past, the form with the perfect infinitive is used: *he can't (cannot) have done it* means "I believe it impossible that he did it" (compare *he must have done it*).

May and might

The verb *may* expresses possibility in either an epistemic or deonic sense, that is, in terms of possible circumstance or permissibility. For example:

The mouse may be dead means that it is possible that the mouse is dead.

In expressing possible circumstance, *may* can have future as well as present reference (*he may arrive* means that it is possible that he will arrive; *I may go to the mall* means that I am considering going to the mall).

The preterite form *might* is used as a synonym for *may* when expressing possible circumstance (as can *could* – see above). It is sometimes said that *might* and *could* express a greater degree of doubt than *may*. *May* (or *might*) can also express irrelevance in spite of certain or likely truth: *He may be taller than I am, but he is certainly not stronger* could mean "While it is (or may be) true that he is taller than I am, that does not make a difference, as he is certainly not stronger."

May can indicate presently given permission for present or future actions: *You may go now*. *Might* used in this way is milder: *You might go now if you feel like it*. Similarly *May I use your phone?* is a request for permission (*might* would be more hesitant or polite).

When used with the perfect infinitive, *may have* indicates uncertainty about a past circumstance, whereas *might have* can have that meaning, but it can also refer to possibilities that did not occur but could have in other circumstances. *She may have eaten the cake* (the speaker does not know whether she ate cake). *She might have eaten*

cake (this means either the same as the above, or else means that she did not eat cake but that it was or would have been possible for her to eat cake).

Note that the above perfect forms refer to possibility, not permission (although the second sense of *might have* might sometimes imply permission).

The negated form of *may* is *may not*; this does not have a common contraction (*mayn't* is obsolete). The negation of *might* is *might not*; this is sometimes contracted to *mightn't*, mostly in tag questions and in other questions expressing doubt (*Mightn't I come in if I took my boots off?*).

The meaning of the negated form depends on the usage of the modal. When possibility is indicated, the negation effectively applies to the main verb rather than the modal: *That may/might not be* means "That may/might not-be," i.e. "That may fail to be true." But when permission is being expressed, the negation applies to the modal or entire verb phrase: *You may not go now* means "You are not permitted to go now" (except in rare, spoken cases where *not* and the main verb are both stressed to indicate that they go together: *You may go or not go, whichever you wish*).

Shall and should

The verb *shall* is used in some varieties of English in place of *will*, indicating futurity when the subject is first person (*I shall, we shall*). With second- and third-person subjects, *shall* indicates an order, command or prophecy: *Cinderella, you shall go to the ball!* It is often used in writing laws and specifications: *Those convicted of violating this law shall be imprisoned for a term of not less than three years; The electronics assembly shall be able to operate within a normal temperature range.*

Should is sometimes used as a first-person equivalent for *would* (in its conditional and "future-in-the-past" uses), in the same way that *shall* can replace *will*. *Should* is often used to describe an expected or recommended behavior or circumstance. It can be used to give advice or to describe normative behavior, though without such strong obligatory force as *must* or *have to*. Thus *You should never lie* describes a social or ethical norm. It can also express what will happen according to theory or expectations: *This should work*. In these uses it is equivalent to ought to.

The formal negations are *shall not* and *should not*, contracted to *shan't* and *shouldn't*. The negation effectively applies to the main verb rather than the auxiliary: *you should not do this* implies not merely that there is no need to do this, but that there is a need not to do this. The logical negation of *I should* is *I ought not to* or *I am not supposed to*.

Will and would

Will as a tense marker is often used to express futurity (*The next meeting will be held on Thursday*). Since this is an expression of time rather than modality, constructions with *will* (or sometimes *shall*; see above and at shall and will) are often referred to as the future tense of English, and forms like *will do*, *will be doing*, *will have done* and *will have been doing* are often called the simple future, future progressive (or future continuous), future perfect, and future perfect progressive (continuous). With first-person

subjects (*I, we*), in varieties where *shall* is used for simple expression of futurity, the use of *will* indicates particular willingness or determination. *Will* can express habitual aspect ; for example, *he will make mistakes* may mean that he frequently makes mistakes.

Will also has these uses as a modal:

It can express strong probability with present time reference, as in *That will be John at the door*.

Modal uses of the preterite form *would* include:

Would is used in some conditional sentences. Expression of politeness, as in *I would like...* (for "I want") and *Would you (be so kind as to) do this?* (for "Please do this").

Both *will* and *would* can be used with the perfect infinitive (*will have, would have*), either to form the future perfect and conditional perfect forms already referred to, or to express perfect aspect in their other meanings (e.g. *there will have been an arrest order*, expressing strong probability).

Must

The modal *must* expresses obligation or necessity: *You must use this form; We must try to escape*. It can also express a conclusion reached by indirect evidence (e.g. *Sue must be at home*). An alternative to *must* is the expression *have to* or *has to* depending on the pronoun (in the present tense sometimes *have got to*), which is often more idiomatic in informal English when referring to obligation. This also provides other forms in which *must* is defective. When used with the perfect infinitive (i.e. with *have* and the past participle), *must* has only an epistemic flavor: *Sue must have left* means that the speaker concludes that Sue has left. To express obligation or necessity in the past, *had to* or some other synonym must be used.

The formal negation of *must* is *must not* (contracted to *mustn't*). However the negation effectively applies to the main verb, not the modality: *You must not do this* means that you are required not to do this, not just that you are not required to do this. To express the lack of requirement or obligation, the negative of *have to* or *need* (see below) can be used: *You don't have to do this; You needn't do this*.

The above negative forms are not usually used in the sense of a factual conclusion; here it is common to use *can't* to express confidence that something is not the case (as in *It can't be here* or, with the perfect, *Sue can't have left*).

Mustn't can nonetheless be used as a simple negative of *must* in tag questions and other questions expressing doubt: *We must do it, mustn't we? Mustn't he be in the operating room by this stage?*

Ought to and had better

Ought is used with meanings similar to those of *should* expressing expectation or requirement. The principal grammatical difference is that *ought* is used with the *to*-infinitive rather than the bare infinitive, hence *we should go* is equivalent to *we ought*

to go. Because of this difference of syntax, *ought* is sometimes excluded from the class of modal verbs, or is classed as a semi-modal.

Ought can be used with perfect infinitives in the same way as *should* (but again with the insertion of *to*): *you ought to have done that earlier*. The grammatically negated form is *ought not* or *oughtn't*, equivalent in meaning to *shouldn't* (but again used with *to*).

The expression *had better* has similar meaning to *should* and *ought* when expressing recommended or expedient behavior: *I had better get down to work* (it can also be used to give instructions with the implication of a threat: *you had better give me the money or else*). The *had* of this expression is similar to a modal: it governs the bare infinitive, it is defective in that it is not replaceable by any other form of the verb *have*, and it behaves syntactically as an auxiliary verb.

Dare and need

The verbs *dare* and *need* can be used both as modals and as ordinary conjugated (non-modal) verbs. As non-modal verbs they can take a *to*-infinitive as their complement (*I dared to answer her*; *He needs to clean that*), although *dare* may also take a bare infinitive (*He didn't dare go*). In their uses as modals they govern a bare infinitive, and are usually restricted to questions and negative sentences. Examples of the modal use of *dare*, followed by equivalents using non-modal *dare*, where appropriate:

Dare he do it? ("Does he dare to do it?")

The modal use of *need* is close in meaning to *must* expressing necessity or obligation. The negated form *need not* (*needn't*) differs in meaning from *must not*, however; it expresses lack of necessity, whereas *must not* expresses prohibition. Examples:

Need I continue? ("Do I need to continue? Must I continue?")

You needn't water the grass ("You don't have to water the grass"; compare the different meaning of *You mustn't water...*)

Modal *need* can also be used with the perfect infinitive: *Need I have done that?* It is most commonly used here in the negative, to denote that something that was done was (from the present perspective) not in fact necessary: *You needn't have left that tip*.

Used to

The verbal expression *used to* expresses past states or past habitual actions, usually with the implication that they are no longer so. It is followed by the infinitive (that is, the full expression consists of the verb *used* plus the *to*-infinitive). Thus the statement *I used to go to college* means that the speaker formerly habitually went to college, and normally implies that this is no longer the case.

In speech, modal verbs are found in both modes utterances, but if when expressing the speaker himself, subjective, modal verbs are only constituent components of clichés,

emotional expression formulas then in messages to someone about something as part of the predicative core, modal verbs are exponents of a marked component of a special grammatical category of the predicate.

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